

CONSTRUCTION OF WATER MAIN TUNNEL AT BREWERY ROAD

MR. JERRY GRANT, B.E., C.Eng., M.I.E.I., M.I.C.E., M.C.I.W.E.M.
PARTNER, M.C. O'SULLIVAN & CO. LTD.

MR. DENNIS McCARTHY, B.Sc.(Hons), C.Eng., M.I.C.E.
SENIOR RESIDENT ENGINEER, M.C.O'SULLIVAN & CO. LTD.

MR. JAMES SHARKEY, B.Eng.(Hons)
RESIDENT ENGINEER, M.C.O'SULLIVAN & CO. LTD.

Glenbeigh Records Management

F3265136

Joint Paper Presented on 15th January, 1996 to:-

The Institution of Engineers of Ireland - Civil Division
The Institution of Engineers of Ireland - Water & Environmental Section.

Synopsis

This paper describes the design and construction of a 1200mm diameter watermain in tunnel primarily through granite rock for a length of 875m, but including 35 m of soft ground tunnelling. The route was generally under and adjacent to Brewery Road, Stillorgan and the project was to provide a new outlet main from the Dublin Corporation reservoir at Stillorgan to serve Dun Laoghaire, with provision for augmentation of the supply to Dublin City.

1. INTRODUCTION

A new 1200 mm diameter steel pipeline has been constructed in tunnel to provide an outlet from the Dublin Corporation reservoir at Stillorgan to Dun Laoghaire Water Supply Improvement Scheme with provision for future augmentation of the supply to Dublin City. The tunnel, together with the construction of a new valvehouse within the reservoir complex, comprised Contract 1 of the seven contracts which are being implemented under Phase 1 of the Dun Laoghaire Water Supply Improvement Scheme (Fig. 1). The Scheme is funded by the Department of the Environment with substantial assistance from the European Union Cohesion Fund.

The Scheme is designed to provide a new water supply to

the former Borough of Dun Laoghaire area, serving some 56,000 population in the immediate supply area, with additional provision for an increased catchment extending to the N11 dual carriageway.

The Scheme capacity is 39MI/day to cater for domestic and commercial demand, adequate supplies to the harbour area and improved fireflow capacities to meet modern standards. A major aspect of the Scheme is the renewal and rehabilitation of the water supply infrastructure in the area, much of which dates from the original Vartry Scheme of 1865/1870. The older cast iron mains, valves and fittings have suffered severe internal corrosion with graphitisation of the cast iron pipe wall and accumulation of tuberculation within the pipes associated with the corrosivity of the low alkalinity Vartry

water. The typical characteristics of this water are alkalinity of 18-20mg/l as CaCO₃, with Langelier index of approximately -2.0.

The difficulties manifested in the water supply, arising from these conditions, can be briefly summarised as follows:-

- *poor pressure and loss of supply due to the diminished hydraulic capacity of mains.*
- *high demand, associated with excessive leakage.*
- *water quality impairment, including elevated turbidity, colour and iron levels, occasional aquatic animal infestation and the risk of bacteriological contamination through ball hydrants.*
- *lack of capacity for fireflows of the order considered appropriate, particularly in commercial areas where public institutions, hotels, hospitals and nursing homes have been established.*
- *diminished operational control with corroded valves, lack of metering, system monitoring and excessive reliance on booster pumps in critical areas.*

The Scheme was outlined in a Preliminary Report submitted to Dun Laoghaire Corporation

in 1989 and included proposals for a new bulk supply, service storage, strengthening and rehabilitation of the network, including the scraping and relining of existing cast iron mains and total replacement

of badly corroded lengths. It also included a new telemetry control system in conjunction with local district flow and pressure measurement, monitoring of key valves, pumps, reservoir levels and

booster chlorination equipment.

A phase I development of the project is now well in hand and the current state of implementation is as follows (Table 1) :-

Table 1 Dun Laoghaire Water Supply Improvement Scheme - Phase 1 - Implementation

Contract Ref	Description	Status	Contractor
1.	<i>Valve house and Tunnel at Stillorgan</i>	<i>Nearing completion</i>	<i>Murphy International Ltd Murphy Pipelines Ltd</i>
2.	<i>Bulk Transfer Pipelines</i>	<i>In Progress</i>	<i>Ascon Ltd</i>
2A.	<i>Pumping Plant</i>	<i>In Progress</i>	<i>EPS Ltd</i>
3.	<i>Reservoir at Church Road</i>	<i>In Progress</i>	<i>Jons Civil Engineering Ltd</i>
3A.	<i>O.S.E.C. Plant</i>	<i>In Progress</i>	<i>EPS Ltd</i>
4.	<i>Intermediate Level Supply</i>	<i>Contract Documents</i>	<i>Tender early 1996</i>
5/1	<i>Trunk Mains Rehabilitation</i>	<i>Preliminary Report</i>	<i>Tender 1996/97</i>
5/2	<i>Sandycove/Dalkey Mains Rehabilitation</i>	<i>Contract Documents</i>	<i>Tender early 1996</i>
5/3	<i>Killiney/Ballybrack Mains Rehabilitation</i>	<i>Site Investigation</i>	<i>Tenders 1996/1997</i>
6	<i>Church Road Pipelines</i>	<i>Included in 2</i>	<i>Ascon Ltd</i>
7	<i>Telemetry System</i>	<i>Contract Documents</i>	<i>Tender early 1996</i>

2. VALVEHOUSE AND TUNNEL AT STILLORGAN-OVERVIEW

The construction of the valvehouse and tunnel at Stillorgan as part of Contract No.1, now substantially completed by Murphy International Limited/Murphy Pipelines Limited Joint Venture, is the subject matter of this paper.

The Dublin Corporation reservoir at Stillorgan was identified as the logical headworks from which the new supply to Dun Laoghaire should be provided based on security of supply consideration.

This reservoir has substantial residual storage (795Ml when full) and is supplied from two sources, the Vartry and Ballymore Eustace Treatment Plants.

A 900mm pipeline was selected as appropriate to meet the supply requirements of the Dun Laoghaire area. It was obvious that a new outlet main would have to follow Brewery Road from the reservoir to the N11 Stillorgan dual carriageway. The construction of a new main in this road by conventional means would be extremely difficult due to the following factors:-

- the number of existing services included 2 No.27", 1 No.24" and 1 No.15" watermains, all in excess of 100 years old. In addition, the road accommodates sewers, ESB services, telecommunications services, high and low pressure gas mains.
- Brewery Road is an important traffic route connecting the N11 National Primary Route with the Sandyford/

Rathfarnham area and experiences heavy traffic flows.

- the pipeline would necessarily have had to be constructed at significant depths due to crossing services and would accordingly have intercepted the variable granite rockhead profile which would have greatly increased the difficulty and duration of construction.
- high ground levels immediately south of the N11 would have resulted in extreme depths for conventional pipeline construction in order to satisfy the hydraulic gradient requirements.

The complexity of services in Brewery road is evident from the typical plan shown in Fig. 2. In these circumstances, a tunnel option offered considerable benefits in terms of providing an optimum technical solution, with minimum social cost, at a modest construction cost premium.

Discussions with Dublin Corporation indicated the desirability of making provision for a future augmentation to the Dublin City Supply in addition to the immediate Dun Laoghaire requirements. A 1200mm diameter pipeline was decided on for this reason. In practice, this required a tunnel of approximately 1.5m diameter, which is close to the minimum practicable size of small bore

FIGURE 2 : EXISTING SERVICES AT BREWERY ROAD

tunnel. The route of the proposed tunnel is illustrated (cover) and the longitudinal profile of the tunnel is illustrated in Fig.3.

A new manifold building and valve control house was designed to provide modern, secure, and electrically controlled valves on all of the existing and future supplies from the reservoir. In addition, modern metering and pressure monitoring facilities were incorporated on all outlet mains. Flow and pressure data and valve controls are centralised in panels within the building, with facilities for transfer via telemetry to control centres at the Dublin Corporation Waterworks Headquarters at Marrowbone Lane and at George's Place, Dun Laoghaire.

The confines of the existing reservoir site at Stillorgan required construction of the valvehouse within the reservoir embankment, with

deep excavations in the earthen dam and underlying bedrock. This led to the formulation of a design based on interlocking secant piles to form the permanent walls of the sub-structure. An alternative method of construction was subsequently developed by the Contractor in conjunction with the resident engineer and implemented as outlined later in this paper.

3. SITE INVESTIGATIONS

Site Investigations were carried out in two phases as follows:-

- *preliminary site investigations; comprised shell and auger boreholes and rock coring to establish overburden conditions, rock profile and characteristics. Slit trenches were also carried out in Brewery Road to establish the precise*

locations of existing services.

- *detailed site investigations; involved extensive boreholing of soft deposits in the vicinity of the tunnel profile, rock coring and rock classification including RQD, report on discontinuities and detailed geological description. A rock mass rating (RMR) was calculated and an assessment of tunnel support requirements made. A number of packer tests were carried out to indicate permeability and a series of trial blasts were also conducted with measurement of peak particle velocity from which vibration attenuation profiles were derived.*

Fig.3 shows the longitudinal profile of the tunnel, the ground profile and the interpreted rockhead profile. In general, the rock is a moderately strong granite with areas of weathered rock which is moderately weak and with occasionally highly weathered zones of very weak rock.

The Packer tests indicated varied rock permeability which corresponded with the variability in the rock quality. Lugeon values derived from three coreholes showed a range of 0-84 lugeons. The relatively low permeability corresponded with good rock and tight joint spacing but permeability increased significantly in weathered sections.

A minimum or idealised cross-section was evolved for tunnelling in sound competent rock which could be expected to be self-supporting. In recognition of the fact that intermittent and occasionally continuous support would be required, an enlarged profile was developed to accommodate this support. This profile was the basis for excavation pay-line measurement.

The rock mass classification "RMR" (Bieniawski 1989) was carried out by Bernard Murphy & Associates as part of the site investigations. This took account of strength, rock quality, RQD, discontinuity spacing and condition, and groundwater conditions. It also took into account other factors such as discontinuity orientation relative to tunnel drive direction, presence of major faults or fractures and the effect of blasting damage.

Average RMR values for each hole were adjusted for discontinuity sets, major faults and blasting damage to give five adjusted RMR values corresponding to 5 categories, very favourable, favourable, fair, unfavourable and very unfavourable. These values were assigned estimated stand-up time for unsupported 1500mm tunnel. Where the adjusted RMR value exceeded 35, it was considered that no support was required and this was confirmed in practice. For values below 35, stand-up times were indicated. The NGI Q-System of rock mass classification based on a

numerical assessment of the rock mass quality using 6 parameters (Barton 1983) was used as a check on 2 boreholes. The parameters used were RQD, number of joint sets, roughness of the most unfavourable joint set, degree of alteration or filling along the weakest joint set, water inflow and stress condition. These values were in good agreement with the RMR values obtained. This information was primarily issued to assist the Contractors with their tenders and in the planning of the works, as it advised them of the general support that might be required on site.

A decision on the actual support to be installed, however, was taken following an inspection of the tunnel face during construction.

An area of soft ground was identified close to the reservoir where the tunnel crosses diagonally under Brewery Road. The term "soft" ground is used here in a tunnelling context to differentiate between tunnelling in rock and tunnelling in clays and gravels. This section involved approximately 35 metres of soft ground tunnelling in clays and gravels. The characteristics of this area indicated glacial origin with pockets of gravel in a predominantly clay matrix.

Accordingly, provision had to be made for soft ground tunnelling, with full support through this section, together

with provision for pre-stabilisation works in the gravel strata in the vicinity of the tunnel profile.

Provision was made in the Contract for additional Geotechnical Investigations in order to optimise the Contractor's approach to ground stabilisation and tunnel support. The additional work would verify and further define the hydrogeological conditions and provide monitoring facilities during grouting.

The site investigations also included pre-contract blasting trials to assess vibration levels and their attenuation in the granite. The resulting peak particle velocity measurements and a regression curve derived from the data were provided to the Contractor and were used to assess the limits imposed in the Contract.

4. TUNNEL DESIGN AND CONTRACT DOCUMENTS

The tunnel was designed as a series of four straight drives with two terminal shafts, one within the Stillorgan Reservoir complex and the other within school grounds at Ardagh. Three intermediate shafts were provided at bends, one located in Leopardstown Park, one at the traffic island at the Brewery Road junction with the N11 and the third immediately south of the N11 in private school grounds. The Contract also included approximately 70m of 900 mm

pipeline in open trench construction from the end of the tunnel to the interface with Contract No.2 at Ardagh Park.

The key elements of the tunnel design were as follows:-

- *the plan route of the tunnel was determined by the shafts located at suitable sites and avoiding crossing under buildings.*
- *the vertical alignment was designed to maintain a minimum gradient of 1 in 500 to ensure satisfactory venting of air and achieve good cleansing during scour-out, minimum cover to the crown of the tunnel of approximately 5 m under the N11, approximately 3.5 m below the rockhead.*
- *the section of tunnel from shaft 2 to shaft 1 was constructed at greater depth and steeper gradient. This afforded increased protection to the old watermains directly over the tunnel. Even at this depth, however, the tunnel profile intercepted the soft ground valley for some 35m.*

The Contract documents were based on the standard conditions of Contract, (third edition, IEI, 1990) together with CESMM method of measurement. The method of measurement, however, was modified in accordance with the recommendations of the CIRIA Working Party on "Tunnelling Improved Contract Practices".

The Bills of Quantities provided for measurement of water control (provision of means and operation, i.e., establishment of pumps, pipework, etc.), ground stabilisation through pre-grouting and the provision of steel arches and lagging as support to the tunnel, as required. The system of rollers and methodology for the installation of the steel pipeline within the tunnel was defined as a Contractor's design and construct item.

5. TENDERS AND COMMENCEMENT OF CONTRACT

In mid 1994, tenders were received following Public Advertisement in the National Press and EU Journal.

Alternatives based on pipe jacking techniques and on the use of tunnel boring machines were offered. However, given the variability of rock and soft ground conditions, it was felt that conventional tunnelling techniques offered the best chance of successful achievement through the various conditions with minimum financial risk to the client.

Accordingly, the tender of Murphy International Limited/Murphy Pipelines Limited, Joint Venture, was recommended and accepted at approximately IR£5,220,000, including VAT. The Contractor commenced work in October, 1994.

6. OVERVIEW OF CONSTRUCTION

The tunnel has now been constructed substantially as designed, using drill and blast techniques through the granite rock. Precast concrete segments were used as the primary support through the soft ground area with considerable success.

In addition, the Contractor constructed a further 55 m of tunnel at the Ardagh end to reduce the length of open cut pipeline. This extended use of tunnelling reflected the benefits of tunnelling in minimising the social impact of pipeline construction at depth in rock. Through this length of tunnelling, the Contractor winched 900mm ductile iron pipes, with Tyton joints.

7. SHAFT CONSTRUCTION

A total of 5 shafts were constructed at either end and at changes of direction on the tunnel (cover diagram).

Shafts 2 and 4 were drive shafts which had to be constructed at the outset to facilitate tunnelling. These two shafts were also required to be enlarged to accommodate insertion of the steel pipeline lengths at a later stage.

At shafts 1 and 5, a range of pipework specials connect the tunnel main to the ductile iron

connecting pipework. At shaft 3, a 1000 mm branch and isolating valves were incorporated to provide for a future connection to Dublin Corporation. These were accommodated in a reinforced concrete chamber.

The shafts varied in depth from 6.5 m at shaft 5, to 11.6 m at shaft 1, with between 1 and 5 m of overburden. The rock quality in shafts 2 and 3 was very strong granite. In shafts 1, 4, and 5, however, a much greater degree of weathering was present with reduced stand-up time.

The construction of the shafts proceeded as follows:-

- *the overburden was excavated to rockhead using a track machine and a circular support system was installed based on structural steel rings and lagging. The steel was preferred by the Contractor to conventional pre-cast concrete (PCC) segments for speed of erection, flexibility and cost. The annulus between the steel rings and the rock was grouted from the surface.*
- *in general, the first couple of metres of bedrock was excavated by rock breaker within the weathered zone.*
- *below approximately 5-6 m, the rock was removed by drill and blast techniques with broken rock loaded by mini excavator into skips*

- *the weathered nature of the rock in shafts 1, 4 and 5 required that the support system in the overburden be continued through the rock to the shaft bottom.*

Safety of workmen was of paramount importance in relation to the shafts. The steel rings were carried to 200mm over ground level to prevent small objects falling into the shaft. Robust handrails, with mesh over-lay, were erected around the perimeter.

8. ROCK BLASTING IN SHAFTS

The irregular random nature of the jointing in the granite bedrock facilitated exposure of a free face on which blast patterns could be arranged. A maximum of 19 chargeholes was used, each charged on a separate time delay of 20 milliseconds, in a total duration of 360 milliseconds.

Protection against flyrock was clearly a priority. Each individual drill hole was covered with sandbags and overlaid in steel plates and concrete kentledge blocks.

A steel mesh safety cover was also provided at the top of the shaft. This also functioned as a security cover while the site was closed down.

Following completion of shaft excavation to formation, a concrete base was constructed, incorporating a drainage sump for tunnel de-watering. Water

flows were somewhat unpredictable, with low inflows in strong granite and increased flows where the rock was weathered. This was most notable in poor rock under the Brewery stream where the ingress increased substantially.

Electrically operated (3-phase) submersible pumping plant was established with a stilling tank to settle out suspended solids before discharge to the Brewery stream. A flow-meter was fitted to the rising main to monitor flows. The finished levels in the shaft were arranged to accommodate the running tracks for muck transport and the support systems required for the pipe installation.

9. ROCK EXCAVATIONS IN TUNNELS

A standard blast pattern was established for rock excavation in the tunnels. A 100mm reamer hole was maintained in the face which acted as a free face for the blast. 19 No. 40mm charged holes were used to provide a clear tunnel section of approximately 1.5 metres diameter.

These holes were drilled by Holman compressed air rock drills on air legs. Typically, each round required approximately 1.5 hours of drilling, though this obviously varied depending on the rock quality.

The 100 mm reamer hole was drilled by a bogey mounted single boom drifter drill. This

hole was drilled 18 m ahead of the tunnel face, equivalent to approximately 1.5 weeks production. It served as a forward probe by means of which the geological conditions ahead of the tunnelling could be anticipated.

Following each blast, the tunnel was ventilated by a compressed air driven air mover through 150 mm PVC ducting. The atmosphere at the face immediately following a blast is one of low oxygen concentration with the presence of oxides of nitrogen and carbon. Air ventilation is used to force clean air to the face to displace these gases and replenish the oxygen levels.

The miners re-entered the tunnel approximately 45-50 minutes after the blast. It was critical to maintain the ventilation close to the face while mucking out since the blast gases are entrained in the muck pile and continue to be released. Over exposure to blast fumes can result in severe headaches and general fatigue due to oxygen deficiency. The ventilation system and procedures, therefore, were designed to prevent this occurrence.

The rock debris was mucked out by hand in bogey mounted skips and transported on rails to the shaft using 1.7 tonne Clayton electric locos. The skips were hoisted to the surface by 22 RB crane and emptied to waste skips.

The complete cycle of drilling, charging, firing, ventilation and mucking out took typically 4 hours.

In normal conditions, without any blasting restrictions, the Contractor achieved two blasts per day per face, each involving approximately 1.2m pull, giving 12m per week advance of the tunnel face. Fig. 4 illustrates the tunnel cross-section details with and without support including pipe support to the rock details.

Before commencing tunnelling, consideration had to be given to the methods used to establish the tunnel drives. It was necessary to form an "eye" to initiate the tunnelling from the drive shaft. The "eye" of the tunnel is an area of high stress concentration and requires to be considered in the same way as any other portal in rock. The support required and construction methods depended on the nature of the rock encountered. For

10. COMMENCEMENT OF TUNNEL AT SHAFT

example, in shaft 4, where the rock showed a high degree of weathering and fracturing, it

was necessary to use 1.82m ID concrete segments for the first 4m of drive from 4-3 and 4-5, with excavation by manual techniques. Installation of the rings provided effective support to the tunnel portal allowing the tunnel drive to proceed efficiently.

Elsewhere, the rock was generally competent and only very local support at the tunnel/shaft interface was necessary. The first 1m to 2m of the tunnels were excavated using mechanical rock breakers on mini-excavators. This was considered more satisfactory than blasting to establish the tunnel profile at the shaft face, primarily due to the shallow rock cover and potential high stress concentrations at the opening portals.

11. GENERAL SAFETY PROCEDURES

Safety in tunnel construction involved strict compliance with B.S. 6164 : 1990, Code of Practice for Safety in Tunnelling and the Construction Industry. Safety hazards were identified by a process of risk analysis applied to the method of working and in development of temporary works to maintain the adequacy and integrity of construction at all times. A rigorous hard hat policy was pursued throughout the site.

At the outset of the contract, a safety induction course was provided for all staff by the

contractor's senior safety representative. The induction course covered responsibilities under the Safety, Health and Welfare at Work Act, 1989, working in confined spaces and general construction regulations.

The following safety procedures and systems were in operation throughout the contract:

- *All operatives in the tunnel had immediate access to an MSA self rescue kit which would provide 12 minutes oxygen at walking pace or 30 minutes at rest.*
- *Ventilation at each working face was initiated 30 minutes before the start of each shift.*
- *A gas detection unit was carried by the leading miner into the tunnel and retained at the working face throughout the shift.*
- *A tally system was operated at each shaft to identify what personnel were underground at any particular time.*
- *At the end of the shift, or whenever a shaft compound was unmanned, a steel mesh safety cover was placed over each shaft to prevent access by intruders. It should be noted that each site was protected by 2.4m high chainlink fencing or solid hoarding of similar height.*
- *A DAC communication system was established to allow the workforce at the tunnel face to communicate with the banksman at the shaft.*

- *The rescue services were familiarised with the tunnel site in the event that they might be required.*

A weekly safety audit was carried out on site jointly by Contractor and R.E. staff. The Contractor carried out weekly examination of all excavations and supports and signed Reports were produced (equivalent to U.K. Factories Act, 1955 Form F91B).

12. BLASTING PROCEDURES AND HANDLING OF EXPLOSIVES

Blasting was carried out on the site in accordance with British Standard Code of Practice for the Safe Use of Explosives in the Construction Industry, B.S. 5607:1988. The explosive used was nitro-glycerine based Frangex produced by Irish Industrial Explosives. It was supplied in 0.18kg sticks. The amount of explosives, numbers and types of delay required for each days working were ordered by telephone from the plant at Enfield on the previous day.

The detonators used were short delay electric detonators, with 30 millisecond delay between 0 and 360 milliseconds, requiring a minimum of 0.3 amps for initiation. An experienced shot firer was nominated by the Contractor, who was responsible for the procurement, handling and use of explosives.

The shot firer was responsible for transport of the explosives from Enfield each morning. This was achieved using a timber lined transit van with the explosives and detonators conveyed in separate locked wooden containers. The van was accompanied at all times by plain clothed armed Gardai as escort, who accounted for the whereabouts and use of each stick of explosive and each detonator.

The explosives were primed at the work face with the detonator inserted into the explosive, well away from any electrical source. When the face was fully charged, each detonator was connected back to the firing cable through the tunnel and up the shaft, isolated from the other tunnel

services. The face would not be charged either during an electrical storm or in the event that an electrical storm was forecast.

When all services were withdrawn from the face, out of range of the fly rock (about 20m) and the tunnel cleared of personnel, the shot firer would evacuate the area and implement the following public warning/safety procedures:

- *A siren was sounded three times one minute before the blast was due and again immediately before each blast.*
- *Traffic and pedestrians were stopped immediately adjacent to the shaft.*
- *The shot firer was required*

to liaise with the shift engineer to ensure that all the vibrometers (a minimum of 3 No.) were set up and scanning.

- *When these procedures were satisfied, the shot firer detonated the round. A final siren was sounded when the shot firer was satisfied that the blast had been successfully completed.*

Following detonation and a period of ventilation, the face was carefully inspected by the lead miner and pit boss. Depending on the integrity of the arching achieved, they decided on the degree of support required.

Scaling down of loose rock was carried out in a systematic

Table 2 Vibration Limits for Tunnel Blasting

Structures	Frequency Range Hz		
	Less than 50	50-100	Greater than 100
Cast iron water and gas mains	12	15	20
Other utility services	15	20	25
Reservoir embankment and valve House	10	15	20
All other buildings and structures	10	15	20

sheeting as lagging, tightly packed to the rock. In crossing under an existing culvert and stream valley, close to the tunnel crown, precast concrete segments were used to line the tunnel.

13. ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

Vibration limits were set down in the specification for monitoring of vibrations associated with work. These set peak particle velocity limits for a range of frequencies as shown in Table 2, to provide for protection of residential property, the reservoir embankment at Stillorgan and most critically, the existing cast iron watermains on Brewery Road which are in excess of 100 years old.

Vibrometers were procured and deployed for all blasts to provide a visual measurement and permanent trace recording of the velocity of the shock waves measured as peak particle velocity in mm/sec and the frequency measured in Hz. The specification recognised that higher peak particular velocities could be tolerated at higher frequencies.

FIGURE 5 : REGRESSION CURVE DRIVE 2 - 1

The instrumentation provided for measurement of vibration peak particle velocity in three perpendicular directions, together with frequency. The instrument used was the Vibrock V401. This was a small light weight but robust instrument which was easily set up under site conditions. In addition to shock wave velocity and frequency, it measured the air over pressure, i.e., the magnitude of the airwave produced by the blast.

As a minimum, three Vibrographs were set up at critical locations, generally at the properties nearest to the blast or mounted on critical structures to be monitored. The output of the vibrograph readings were provided to the supervising engineers on a daily basis by the Contractor.

With the vibration monitoring results, details of the corresponding blast pattern were provided, i.e., number of holes, charge rate and chainage from the shaft. This provided a facility for tracing

any blasts which indicated an exceedance of the limits. Using the results, it was also possible to plot regression curves from which likely vibration levels could be predicted for any site, relative to a blast location and charge weight. A typical regression envelope is shown in Fig. 5.

A total of 947 blasts were detonated on the project. Less than 3% indicated an exceedance of the specification limits. These generally arose in relation to service pipes, where a degree of relaxation of the specification limits was permitted following careful evaluation on site.

Given the proximity of these services to the blasting, it was found to be extremely difficult to comply with the initial specification limits. Detailed tests were carried out to establish a safe threshold value which would allow the specification to be modified without risk to the services.

Essentially, the twin 27", 24" and 15" cast iron watermains on Brewery Road were

directly over or in close proximity to the tunnel drive for approximately 70m of its length, with 35m in hard granite rock. The distance from the tunnel crown to the services was between 6 - 7m.

As the tunnel progressed, close to these pipes, the maximum instantaneous charge (MIC) was limited to the minimum practicable weight of one stick (0.18kgs). The vibrations recorded in the region of the pipes was generally 20-30mm/sec. These values were approximately twice the limits originally specified. Therefore, it was necessary to examine the response of the pipes to the higher values in order to determine whether the specification limits could be relaxed and what limits should be set in practice.

Accordingly, an experiment was conducted as follows:

- *The mains were exposed and a chamber was constructed on the pipelines in which a transducer was fixed permanently on the pipe. The chamber was then backfilled with sand and compacted to simulate as closely as possible the actual conditions of the pipe.*
- *A section of 27" pipe had been removed as part of the pipe connection work and this was analysed by Forbairt indicating an ultimate tensile strength of 110N/mm².*

- *Strain gauges were fitted to the cast iron pipes at this location on Brewery Road which allowed the stress induced by blasting to be recorded.*
- *At an MIC of 0.18kgs, no measurable stress was recorded in the pipe. Increasing the charge rate to 0.27kgs indicated a stress of 0.3N/mm² at a distance of approximately 7m from the face.*
- *It was noted that truck loading induced a stress of up to 1.5N/mm² in the pipe.*
- *This arrangement allowed us to make direct comparisons between the stress induced on the pipe and the peak particle velocity recorded.*

For an MIC of 0.27kgs, the peak particle velocity measured was 30mm/s. As stated, this was accompanied by an induced stress of the order of .3N/mm², whereas Forbairt were of the opinion that a stress of up to 11N/mm² or 10% of the tensile strength of the pipe could be tolerated. This factor of safety was necessary given that there could be varying degrees of corrosion of the pipewall and also that slight movements at the joint could induce leakage. Ultimately, it was decided that a maximum peak particle velocity of 50mm/s was the upper limit. This value would be regarded as satisfactory for pressurised line pipe based on research undertaken by the U.S. Bureau of Mines.

The specified vibration limits for properties generally (12-15mm/s) would be considered to be well below levels likely to cause even minor cosmetic damage, by reference to available standards such as B.S. 7385, Part 2 : 1982, research by Langefors (Sweden), U.S. Bureau of Mines, etc. Nevertheless, these vibrations are perceptible to the public. Human sensitivity varies enormously, with some people and indeed animals being highly sensitive to them. This was borne out by the experience of this project. Therefore, even though higher values would be unlikely to cause superficial damage to building fabric, they would be inadvisable where the public are concerned.

Apart from vibrations, it is important to control noise, air blast and air over pressure. Excessive air blast would cause broken window panes, so that screens were installed at each tunnel entrance. These also helped to reduce the noise associated with the blast (maximum specified air over-pressure was 120 db).

14. PUBLIC RELATIONS

The use of explosives in a built up urban environment at Stillorgan involved considerable public liaison and resulted in a degree of public reaction, particularly from local residents. Public relations are, therefore, of critical importance where blasting is concerned because

blasting gives rise to natural complaints and concerns. In order to alleviate this concern, the following steps were taken:

- A pre-commencement bulletin was issued throughout the local area, describing the works and programme.
- Pre-works defects surveys were carried out on properties within a 30m radius of the tunnel by an independent surveyor. These surveys endeavoured to assess the condition of the premises and identify structural defects.
- Circulars were issued to householders in the area outlining the contractor's proposed works schedule, the requirement for blasting, the precautions being taken and giving the names and numbers of contact personnel.
- A complaint procedure was established whereby all representations from the public whether by telephone, in person or written, were logged and processed in a systematic fashion.

In general, the residential properties in this area are relatively modern (30 years and less). Properties of this nature exhibit significant hairline cracking of plaster work, shrinkage cracking of timber, particularly soft wood and other minor defects. It is not practicable to record all such defects in a general pre-works survey. However, the heightened sensitivity of the householder to the potential for damage can result in claims that all such cracks noticed subsequent to the

works are regarded as resulting from vibration loading. In fact, residents tend not to be aware of long-term cracks until after blasting has taken place.

A consistent approach is necessary to public relations as shown Fig. 6. This approach provides for:

- A quick, courteous and factual response.
- A request to the complainant for a written statement of the specific complaint, using a pro-

FIGURE 6 : PUBLIC COMPLAINT PROCESSING PROCEDURE

forma approach.

- *A site visit is essential in response to a complaint of alleged damage.*
- *Where damage was alleged, vibration monitoring was initiated at that site, over and above monitoring being carried out by the Contractor. In addition, crack measuring "tell-tales" were placed on alleged cracks to determine whether further movement was taking place.*
- *The householder was advised of the vibration records at the property and at properties closer to the blasting. These were related to specification limits and the basis of these was explained relative to the risk of damage to property.*
- *Householders were also free to employ independent engineers/architects and in these cases, such professionals were given free access to the records and the procedures being employed. In general, this proved very satisfactory with an appreciation on the part of such professional personnel that the work posed no threat to property.*
- *In some cases, other causes of damage were noted and identified. For example, building works within a property or the effects of drying out associated with the particularly dry summer of 1995 was a factor in inducing cracking of boundary walls.*

While most people were generally satisfied with this approach, inevitably, there were some who doubted the validity of the technical arguments presented to them. It was therefore decided that Forbairt should be engaged to carry out random independent monitoring of blasting operations and to provide reports which would afford independent validation of the monitoring being carried out by the Contractor and resident engineering teams. Their findings were forwarded to the householders on request.

Apart from representations to the Contractor and Resident Engineers, members of the public also made representations to technical officials and elected members of Dun Laoghaire Rathdown County Council. All such complaints were processed in the same way and similar factual reports were provided to the County Council so that consistent responses were issued from whatever source. This consistency of approach is essential to successful management of the public relations.

At the conclusion of the work, there are no major issues outstanding in relation to the public. It is possible that some householders may pursue claims alleging minor cracking. However, any damage alleged to date is limited to minor cracking which we are satisfied is not necessarily the fault of the blasting and is of no structural consequence. Furthermore,

we believe that there are comprehensive records for all blasting events which will facilitate objective evaluation of any future claims.

15. SOFT GROUND STABILISATION

The site investigations identified an apparent "drowned valley" for a length of approximately 35m along the route of the tunnel. The majority of boreholes had encountered a stiff brown boulder clay, which would be a satisfactory tunnelling medium. However, one borehole had identified a lens of sandy gravel within the tunnel horizon. Other boreholes had shown similar lenses above the tunnel horizon, indicating the possibility that these gravel deposits might be linked with the potential for significant water inflows to the tunnel.

Sand and gravel strata have little plasticity or cohesion and can be unstable as tunnelling media. A small fall of material at a tunnel face can undermine the arching action and result in progressive collapse. Where deposits are saturated, hydrostatic pressure on the face may cause collapse. This can result in settlement at ground level and possible damage to critical services located over the tunnel. For these reasons, pre-treatment of gravels may be required.

To deal with the gravels, the Contract Documents provided

for pre-stabilisation by injection of cement bentonite grout to improve the strength and impermeability characteristics of the gravels. The documents envisaged the use of double packer “tube-a-manchettes” grouting of the tunnel profile and in the surrounding soils to at least a tunnel diameter from the tunnel profile. The Contract Documents also provided for additional grouting from within the tunnel using chemical grouts, should this be required. They also provided for further site investigations to quantify and precisely define the materials and conditions to be encountered. In view of the fact that Brewery Road is a major traffic route, it was highly desirable to minimise traffic disruption during the grouting work. The approach adopted by the Contractor on site was generally as follows:

- An additional 6 no. boreholes were constructed to further define and establish the extent of the gravel.
- Pump tests were carried out to determine whether the various gravel strata were connected and to establish the permeability of the soils. These tests indicated that the individual gravel lenses appeared to be isolated from each other.
- Of the 35m of soft tunnelling, it was established that the gravels could be expected to be encountered after some 15m of clay.

- Surface grouting of the gravels over this length was embarked upon by drilling from the adjacent carpark to a defined pattern.
- The grout used was varied depending on the conditions. The basic mix

was 0.45 water/cement ratio with a trixotrophic agent introduced to prevent excessive spread of the grout.

- As each grout hole was drilled, the materials arising were identified and carefully logged. This

FIGURE 7 : GROUTING OF GRAVEL ZONES

FIGURE 8 : SEQUENCE OF GROUTING OPERATION

further assisted in clarifying the nature and extent of the gravels needed to be treated on site.

As stated, a grouting compound was established in a carpark of the Leopardstown Inn adjacent to Brewery Road and the entire grouting operation was carried out from this carpark while maintaining traffic flows on the road. This approach also helped to avoid contact with the nest of services in Brewery Road. It was necessary to drill at raked angles between 5° and 50° to the vertical. (Fig. 7)

The boreholes extended sufficiently deep to ensure that the clay had been fully penetrated below the gravel horizon. The casings were withdrawn in 0.5m stages with grout pumped in at low pressures (0.2 bar) using a single packer. (Fig. 8) The pressures were strictly controlled to avoid potential ground heave which could have put the existing services at risk. A total of 16m³ of grout was used, in a total of 45 holes, over a 4 week period.

Level monitoring pins were fixed on saddles onto the cast iron pipes so that the levels of the mains could be constantly monitored during the pumping operation. In the event, no movement was indicated. Use of extensimeters was considered but deemed impractical. An open trench, covered by road plates, was formed to facilitate visual inspection of the pipes.

Values of ± 5mm movement and angular distortion of 1:1000 along the pipes were adopted as trigger limits for cessation of grouting. However, these limits were not reached.

On completion of the grouting, a trial core was taken to establish the extent of stabilisation of the gravels. After a first unsuccessful attempt at recovering a core, a second core was successfully taken and indicated considerable cementitious accumulation and moderate strength within the gravel matrix. This indicated that tunnelling could proceed with caution.

16. SOFT GROUND TUNNELLING

Working from Shaft 2, the granite/boulder clay interface was uncovered at chainage 154, which was very close to the expected intersection from the site investigation data. It is also worth noting that the granite was extremely competent up to the interface with the clay. The interface had also been identified in advance of the tunnelling by forward probing. When finally broken through, the clay face was remarkably dry and proved to be a good tunnelling medium with a reasonable stand-up time as predicted. The stability of the clay face had been assessed using the

$$\text{O'Reilly formula } \left(N = \frac{\gamma h}{C_u} \right)$$

which had indicated a

reasonable stability number of 2.6.

The primary support system in the soft ground comprised 1.68m I.D. PCC segments. The clay was manually excavated and an average of four rings per shift were achieved, equivalent to 2.4m per day.

The clay/gravel interface was struck at chainage 175. Notwithstanding the evidence from the trial core, it became clear that the gravels remained relatively loose and permeable, with significant water inflow. Forward probing indicated that no significant improvement could be expected in the gravels for at least 2.4m. It was decided, therefore, to box up the face and inject more grout at the interface.

In this secondary grouting, a thicker grout was used to reduce the potential for wash out. In total, a further 5m³ of grout was pumped into the interface areas from holes bored directly from Brewery Road. Notwithstanding this additional treatment, the gravels remained relatively loose and did not achieve the strength anticipated.

Tunnelling proceeded very cautiously through the gravels by maintaining the maximum support to the face and crown. The maximum predicted settlement of 5-7mm, based on 2% face loss, was bettered.

Approximately one ring per shift was achieved until the

granite was again encountered at chainage 183. At the granite transition and for the first 2m into the rock, blasting was considered inadvisable due to the risk of shattering the crown with release of water from the waterbearing gravels above. The rock was excavated using air breakers and plug and feather over this length before blasting resumed in the normal way.

17. OVERVIEW OF THE TUNNELLING

Overall, the tunnelling was completed approximately to programme. In general, the tunnelling conditions were broadly as anticipated from the Site Investigation information. Apart from the soft ground area, the rock from shaft 2 to shaft 1 was generally competent. On the other hand, between shafts 2 and 3 and between shafts 4 and 5, rock quality was much more variable and significant sections of this tunnel were supported in steel arches and occasionally with full lagging. Water ingress in these sections was also higher. The tunnel drive 2 > 3 was routed over much of its length under the Brewery stream.

Weathered rock had been anticipated in the crossing under the N11 dual carriageway and provision had been made for the use of precast segments, particularly as the rock cover in this area was lower than elsewhere (3-4m to the crown).

FIGURE 9 : TUNNEL TIME CHAINAGE GRAPH

In the event, the rock under the dual carriageway was particularly competent and required little support.

A second soft ground intrusion was encountered upstream of shaft 3 at Brewery Road near the N11 Junction. This would have generally coincided with the likely original bed of the Brewery Road stream. An 1800 mm culvert carrying the stream crossed in close proximity to the tunnel crown. In this area, the crown of the tunnel became unstable and required surface excavation and placement of concrete together with the use of segments to successfully negotiate the difficult section. This was accomplished without significant disruption of traffic and with minimum delay to the Project.

Overall, the tunnelling in this project is considered to have been extremely successful, providing for the construction of a major 1200mm pipeline in a densely built-up urban environment with minimum social disruption. Fig. 9 shows the time/chainage graphs for various tunnels. The overall construction of the tunnel was completed within programme; tunnel 4 - 5 being on the critical path.

18. INSTALLATION OF STEEL LINER PIPE

Within the tunnel, a 1200 mm pipeline was constructed in 1219 mm OD steel tube, wall thickness 12.7mm, grade X42 steel to API 5LX. The pipe has internal lining in 9mm

cement mortar and 2mm thick external polyethylene sleeve. The pipe was sourced in Finland and lined in Holland.

The procedure for installation of the pipeline was generally as follows:-

- *having cleared the tunnel floor of loose debris, the concrete floor was cast to the gradient of the finished pipeline. A system of neoprene rollers, running on bearings, mounted on steel brackets were installed by bolting into the concrete floor at 5m spacings. The rollers were established to an accuracy of + or - 5mm.*
- *the carbon steel pipes, 6m long, were lowered onto the rollers at the shaft invert and clamped to the end of the previous pipe. The pipes were welded in three passes of butt welds. Each weld was tested by 100% X-radiography.*
- *the external protection of the pipe was completed at the joint by fitting of a heat shrink wrap. A Holiday test was undertaken to identify any defects in the wrapping.*
- *the joint was protected by fitting a steel bandage clamped over shrink-wrap membrane at the joint to prevent damage on the neoprene rollers during winching.*
- *at that stage, the pipeline was drawn forward up the*

tunnel using a 150 ton air driven winch located at the opposite reception shaft. This procedure was repeated using 6m lengths of pipe until each run was completed.

- *the cement mortar lining on the inside face of the pipe was made good by hand.*
- *The bends and connection required at the shafts were manufactured in steel and lined internally and externally by the Contractor.*
- *cathodic protection was provided by the fitting of sacrificial anodes to the pipe at each shaft by specialist Sub-Contractor.*

19. GROUTING OF ANNULAR SPACE

On completion of the pipe installation, the annular void around the pipes was filled in a cement : PFA grout. Timber supports were provided in the roof of the tunnel at crown level to prevent flotation of the pipe during grouting. Concrete bulkheads were formed at the ends of each tunnel length with opes for insertion and proving of the grouting.

The grout used was GM5C, produced by Construction Material Services in the U.K., comprised of a mix of 5 parts PFA to 1 part OPC and was delivered in large (1250kg) plastic laminated bags.

Tests were carried out on the grout to determine thickening times, gel strengths, rheology, compressive strengths in accordance with API standards to prove the suitability of the mix prior to undertaking any work on site.

The operation was originally set up to achieve high grout output levels using a single high press BJ pacemaker triplex pump mounted on a truck of the type used in oil field work, starting at Shaft 4 and pumping tunnel drive 4 < 3 and 4 < 5.

The equipment, although highly effective, proved to be too powerful for the required tasks. The operatives had difficulty in keeping the silo filled with the grout mix materials. There were also some potential environmental problems due to dust arising from the bag discharge into the silo at approximately 8m above ground level.

Following the completion of tunnels 3 > 5 the methods were revised and further

equipment mobilised. This comprised of a low level batching plant, small agitators and grout pumps in a set up detailed in Fig. 10.

The main advantages of this system, which made use of more conventional grouting equipment, were:-

- *The elimination of large elevated silos.*
- *The large powerful cement pump truck was dispensed with.*
- *Bags emptied at ground level approximately, therefore less dust*

emissions and less problems with lumps.

- *Less dust as cement immediately mixed with water.*
- *Little, if any, pollution caused by "washing out" the system.*
- *Screening made easier.*
- *Work could be carried out in the rain and all weathers.*

The environmental issues were particularly important in view of the fact that the plant would need to be located at Shaft 2 in order to grout the remaining tunnel drives, i.e., 2 > 1 and 2 > 3, which was immediately adjacent to the Brewery Road Stream and close to residential properties. Using the equipment, approximately 100 bags (125 tons of grout) was placed in the tunnels on a daily basis filling up the annulus in drive 2 > 3 in approximately three days.

The grout tended to displace water from the tunnel which was discharged through a

series of pipe outlets, in the headwall of the tunnel at the end of the tunnel drive. These pipes were capped off when it was determined that pure grout was flowing through using mud balance tests at the outlet end, i.e., the density of the grout at the outlet end should be consistent with that at mixing end where tests were undertaken hourly.

The grouting continued until a minimum of 1m high standpipe above the tunnel crown was fully filled usually under very little pressure where the tunnel drive sloped away from the point of injection (drive 2>3). For drive 2>1 it was necessary to relocate the plant for the "topping up" to Shaft 1 in order to reduce pumping pressures in the tunnel. To fill the tunnel irregularities during the last stage of pumping, when the grout was present in the vent pipes, a small amount of additional pump pressure (20psi) was used to compress and remove any air present and fill the voids.

Grout cubes were taken hourly and strict quality control procedures were carried out to ensure consistency of mix, etc. On completion of these works and satisfactory hydraulic testing of the pipeline, the shafts are being backfilled and the shaft sites reinstated. No permanent access is deemed necessary for the pipeline.

20. VALVEHOUSE CONSTRUCTION

The valvehouse structure is located at the head of the tunnel in the embankment of Stillorgan reservoir. It was necessary to avoid vibration loading or movement in the embankment of this 19th Century reservoir. The Contractor proposed a King-Post Temporary Works system

for the construction of the Valvehouse sub-structure in preference to the secant piled wall permanent works originally specified. The key elements of this proposal were:-

- *coring through overburden and granite bedrock to install universal column steel sections at approximately 1.8m centres*

which were grouted into the rock

- *erection of a support framework between the columns to provide a rigid support system with minimal displacement of the reservoir embankment.*
- *as the excavation was taken down, timber sleepers were installed and wedged between the universal column sections to provide close support to the excavated face.*
- *following removal of the overburden, the rock excavation for the permanent sump was commenced by stitch drilling of the perimeter to prevent fragmentation of the sound rock retaining the toe of the columns. Excavation proceeded initially by rock breaker and ultimately using drill and blast.*

These operations required to be carried out in close proximity to the existing twin 27 " feeder pipes from Stillorgan reservoir and connecting branch pipes. This required provision of supports, precautions against damage during excavation and blasting and careful staging of the operations.

The valve sump was then constructed as a conventional reinforced concrete sump within the King-Post system. A 1600mm pipe manifold was installed with valved branches to all of the existing trunk

mains and to the new 1200mm tunnel pipeline. New electromagnetic flow meters were installed on each main external to the valve house and each of the existing mains was connected up in a carefully planned and staged operation involving detailed co-operation with Dublin Corporation staff at Stillorgan who implemented the supply shut-downs.

Fig. 11 shows a layout of the valvehouse site with external pipework arrangements. Figs. 12 and Fig. 13 illustrate the pipework arrangement within the valvehouse in plan and section.

The super-structure of the valvehouse was finished externally in cut granite cladding and the pitched roof is clad in a natural stone slate. These finishes are designed to complement the existing screenhouse which dates from the original Vartry Scheme.

The new valvehouse and associated pipework provides for modern valve controls and metering on all of the existing supplies from the Stillorgan Reservoir Complex. Valve controls, flow and pressure data is relayed to panels within the building and facilities have been provided for future integration with the Dublin Corporation and Dun Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council Telemetry System.

SUMMARY

To summarise, a major new pipeline has been constructed using tunnelling techniques in

granite and soft ground between Stillorgan Reservoir and Ardagh to provide a strategic large diameter outlet from the Dublin Corporation Reservoir at Stillorgan.. This outlet main will provide for the future water supply requirements of Dun Laoghaire and of Dublin City itself. In addition, a major new valvehouse was constructed within the reservoir site, located in the reservoir embankment to provide modern valve and meter facilities on the existing supply mains from the reservoir.

The project was successfully completed by Murphy International Limited/Murphy Pipelines Limited Joint Venture, within programme and budget.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Authors wish to thank those who have co-operated with and assisted in the work described in the paper, in particular the following:-

- *Mr. Patrick A.F. Dullaghan, County Engineer, Dun Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council for permission to publish this paper and for his support and co-operation throughout the project.*
- *Mr. Larry Brassill, former Borough Engineer and Project Engineer for the Project, his deputy, Mr. Brendan Butler, Mr. M.P. O'Brien, S.E.E., Mr. Denis Ryan (former E.E.), Mr. Michael Phillips, Senior Engineer, Mr. Terry Rice, S.E.E., and Mr. Michael Rogers, E.E., of the Waterworks Department, together with the supervisors and staff.*
- *Mr. Kevin O'Sullivan, County Manager, Mr. Des Taylor, Assistant County Manager, Ms. Marie Curran, S.S.O. and the administration staff generally.*
- *Mr. Louis Kilmartin, Mr. J.W.J. Anderson and Mr. Tony Cawley, Department of the Environment, for their support and assistance at all stages of the work.*
- *Mr. Jim Fenwick, Dublin City Engineer, his predecessor Mr. Kevin O'Donnell, and Mr. Maurice O'Connell, Deputy City Engineer, Mr. John Bonner, Mr. Ned Fleming and Dublin Corporation Waterworks Staff at Stillorgan for their co-operation and assistance at all stages of the work at Stillorgan*
- *Management and Staff of Murphy International Limited/Murphy Pipelines Limited Joint Venture, who were responsible for construction of the works.*
- *Colleagues in M.C. O'Sullivan & Co. Ltd. who have worked on the design, contract documents and construction supervision of this major scheme.*